

BIOPHILIC PRISON ARCHITECTURE

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Introduction

The design and architecture of prisons involve a range of aspects including ensuring the physical and mental safety of staff and inmates and reducing the escape risk. Besides these, prisons experience daily occurrences such as work, studies, treatment programs and adult and children visits. These activities have to be factored in the architecture and design solutions. In response, prisons agencies strive to incorporate these demands in the form of supportive architecture and design features within a broader framework of supportive environment. This holistic approach holds a gamut of advantages as the physical environment importance is outweighed when incorporated in the program activities development.

Methodology

The main methodology to be employed in the study will be a review of academic literature on how design and architecture are important for inmates in prisons and remand. Data collection will mostly be secondary as it will be done by searching through published data. This research will use government publications, journals that touch on prison designs and mental health, a range of reports, public records, statistical records, and historical documents. The past data collected through the above means, together with online and offline searches will be analyzed, reviewed, and interpreted. A systematic literature review then be conducted.

New materials, websites, and official reports recently published and done in the mentioned area will be used, and the data extracted from them used to update the data in the study. Many of the current literature came upon the topic of prison design and mental health. Still, it will be reduced sizably after analysis of the content of the articles to a good number.

The review aimed to embed the current knowledge in policy discussions and ensure the evidence in existence in relation to the physical prison environment informs the strategic concepts around security and development of prisons and contribute to the discussions. There is limited time and high quality studies in this area of study, which is why a literature review was conducted. There are limitations regarding the certainty of conclusions drawn from these reviews. There is also a language barrier as some studies in this area are not done in English. However, findings of this study align with research in relevant areas and with experience of practitioners in the prison services worldwide.

Findings

There are reasons to believe that design and architecture are crucial for prison services, which are evident in how the physical environment affects the well-being and social relations within the facilities. The results of this study aligns with supportive environment policy used in prisons worldwide starting with the physical environment which enables rehabilitation programmes and dynamic security and reducing isolation during detention. The existing research majorly point to the direction of the study and supports the hypothesis that biophilic design of prisons improves the mental well-being of inmates. On the other hand, there remains an improvement room especially to the existing remand prisons.

Experiences of nature including photographs and films improve cognitive performance and attention capacity and reduce anxiety and stress (DeSesto, 2020). Nature scenes also help patients dealing with pain, aids in health issue recovery and reduce blood pressure and heart rate (Sachs, 2018). The view of nature also tends to improve life satisfaction and reduces aggressive behavior. Access to green spaces, both visually and physically, provides distraction and helps reduce mental fatigue, which is a huge risk in prison settings due to the fact that they can be monotonous and unpleasant to inmates. Mental fatigue results in anger, irritability, aggressive behavior, poor thought process and reduced impulse control. Access to green spaces has been linked to improved attention span and lower aggressiveness rates. Nature views have been found to be restorative and are useful when one seeks to restore calm after experiencing emotionally difficult or threatening events. The positive effect of nature views was found to be strongest higher inmate turnover. Population turnover in closed institutions adds stress to the unit and could lead to increased aggression to both staff and inmates (Seymour, 2019).

The use of green spaces is known as biophilic design which was aimed at bringing nature to city residents to promote positive psychological and physiological outcomes (Sonderlund, 2019). The design has been found to have the similar effects in people in closed institutional environments. Biophilic designs includes the using fractal patterns which can be self replicating and increase to smaller magnification, refuge for a sense of safety, prospect and greenery(Gordonson, 2019). Biophilia as a hypothesis assumes that nature exposure reduces stress and contributes to rapid stress recovery. The incorporation of biophilia in prisons design is an emerging academic and practice field (Ali and McKinlay, n.d). Nature images including wall posters and nature movie screening are increasingly being incorporated in new and rehabilitated

prisons which include the use of green walls, plants and green houses for production of food for prisoners (Moran and Turner, 2019; Moran, 2019).

The above practices have also been referred to as horticulture therapy which refers to the experience to plants between the therapist and the patient. Horticulture therapy can take the form of imagining and viewing nature, visiting healing garden and gardening. It facilitates healing, alleviates stress, increases mental and physical wellbeing and promotes social-life participation and re-employment of people with physical and mental illness. Horticulture therapy has also been found to reduce vulnerability to addiction including psychological symptoms, tension and distress and in turn reduces the use of drugs among participants (Yassein and Ebrahiem, 2018). The practice, however, has to significant impact on building resistance to addiction among participants in terms of increased sense of self efficacy, positive expectations and confidence in coping skills (Ho Schar, Biewenga and Lombawa, 2020).

Biophilic design solutions hold a promise of improved prison services with reduced violence with the improvement of physical conditions such as noise and dilapidation reduction and privacy improvement (Soderlund and Newman, 2017). Staff characteristics and other structural factors such as staff-inmate ratio, crowd influence motivation towards and, or opportunity to engage in serious violence (Rai, Asim and Shree, 2020). Supportive design helps in the achievement of reduction of stress, agitation, irritation and aggression while increasing positive interaction and learning (Tardast, Rajabi and Meshkini, 2020). The choice of prison designs helps mitigate the experiences of inmates of social, emotional and material losses associated with imprisonment (Soderlund, 2017). These include the loss of power, freedom, relationships and objects. The physical environment approach helps compensate for the damage inflicted by high security institutions (Wijesooriya and Brambilla, 2020). Through care-ideology

and rehabilitation, harmful effects of prison terms can be reduced and help inmates acquire skills to enable them live a non-criminal life integrated in the society when freed (Moghaddami, 2019).

Materials, architecture and interiors lay groundwork for a range of positive measures in specially adapted places (Asim and Shree, 2019). The supportive design concept mitigates pains of imprisonment and enables rehabilitative practices.

In the part of staff, improved satisfaction with the physical environment around work helps improve workplace efficiency, increase commitment to work and reduce staff turnover (Toews, Wagenfeld, Stevens and Shoemaker, 2020). Harsher work conditions such as intrusive noise, clutter and prison dilapidation result in reduced well-being characterized by sick leave uses, change in the use of alcohol and tobacco use, somatic symptomology, psychological symptomology and personal worries (Moghaddami, 2019). A physical environment has an important impact on job satisfaction and commitment.

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